
Invited lecture

CURRENT CHALLENGES IN CYBERSECURITY AND INFORMATION SECURITY

*"It takes twenty years to build a reputation and
a few minutes of cyber-incident to ruin it"*
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Abstract

The penetration of information and communication technologies into business activities, public and state administration, and the everyday life of citizens makes it necessary to keep these technologies running to maintain the quality of life of virtually every citizen. Therefore, ensuring the security of information and communication technologies has become an absolute necessity. The EU is trying to harmonise the concept and implementation of cyber security across all Member States based on best practices. To do this, it uses the mechanism of directives, which it issues regularly on topical issues. Currently, the NIS2 directives, which regulate the protection of cyberspace in general in EU countries, and the DORA directive, which unifies the concept of robustness of information systems of financial institutions, are very topical. The paper highlights the benefits of both directives for ensuring cybersecurity in EU countries in particular.

Keywords

Cybersecurity, NIS2, DORA, Internal threats, Cybersecurity

1 Introduction

The pervasiveness of information and communication technologies (ICT) in people's and organizations' daily lives brings an ever-increasing dependence on them. The interconnection of computers and computer networks presents, on the one hand, significant opportunities and speed for data exchange and sharing, and thus providing a better basis for decision-making (Hussein, et al., 2023), for scientific and research work, for the advancement of medical science (Cooper-Jones et al., 2022) and for protection against natural disasters (Gomes, et al., 2016). However, on the other hand, it also brings with it previously unusual and nowadays unexpected risks and threats (Syuntyurenko & Gilyarevskii, 2021). Optimistic ICT Professionals not only highlight the above mentioned benefits and many more (Lesmana, 2023), but the risks and

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threats already remain hidden for many users under the positive side of digitalization (Möhring et al., 2023).

There is, however, a second group of ICT workers, those who protect ICT assets (data, information, processes, and hardware) (ISO/IEC 27000, 2018) from being restricted or even destroyed. This refers to those who deal with cybersecurity and information protection in the organisation's information systems. Information systems security is becoming one of the most critical issues of our time - can I trust my information in my information system, is my information reliable, has someone gained unauthorised access to my system, is someone trying to destroy my data? These and other questions are part of the daily life of department and division managers in enterprise IT today, and they seek answers in collaboration with cybersecurity managers and executives. But how to protect against such threats? There are many tools, and they vary depending on what we primarily want to protect.

Protection against unauthorised, and therefore unauthorised access to the organisation's information system is usually ensured by an information security management system (ISO/IEC 27001, 2022). This is a management system, i.e., its principles follow the general principles that are valid for all other management systems (i.e., PDCA cycle, documentation method, initial risk analysis, etc.). One of the tools of the security management system is the vulnerability analysis. Vulnerability analysis tools tend to be very comprehensive and deal with the analysis of the state of equipment as well as computer networks or web applications (Zhao et al., 2022), the linking of information systems in cyberspace (Liu et al., 2022), remote access to the system, etc.

Threats to an organisation's information systems and information are usually assumed to be from external sources-attacks from outside. Less expected are internal attacks and mistakes and failures of its own employees. The situation with the types of external attacks on an organization's information systems is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: The most common types of external attacks on information systems of organizations

Source: (Verizon Business, 2024)

It can be seen from Fig. 1 that the most common form is the popular flooding of the organization's communication channel (DoS attack), which, in terms of frequency, is followed by unauthorized attempts to break into the organization's information systems (System Intrusion).

The protection of individual information assets is not such a simple matter, as the assets are threatened not only by generally assumed external threats, but also internal threats are gradually gaining in strength and frequency (Hološka & Doucek, 2024). These threats are not limited to data loss per se, but can also take a purely destructive form (Payne et al., 2022). Frustrated privileged users, may one day decide to make unpunished changes to corporate or production infrastructure to vent frustration, point out unresolved issues, or damage the company's reputation (Press Release, 2022). Particularly vulnerable are drinking water processing and supply, or fuel and electricity distribution (Abrams & Weiss, 2008). Generally, these are critical infrastructures of a country or even an entire society. Another profound impact these threats can cause is the leakage of intellectual property. The latter can be liquidating for the company in terms of competitiveness in the market. Years of development and research will be leaked to competitors in a matter of days and the competitive advantage in the market will disappear overnight. The economic impact in the form of stock market losses can wipe out years of organizational work and long periods of positive economic performance in months (Bunn & Scott, 2017).

The costs incurred in dealing with insider incidents are also rising permanently year-on-year, not only in individual categories but also overall. Their development in large organisations between 2018 and 2022 can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Fig. 2: Impact of insider incidents in 2018 - 2022 in millions of USD

Source: (Ponemon Institute, 2023)

Before we start looking at how to address the protection of information systems assets in organizations, let us look at the situation in the world, where and how safe which countries are from a cybersecurity perspective. Various organisations worldwide survey cybersecurity conditions from their perspective, which they publish in various indices. For this article, I have selected some countries whose citizens are participating in this conference. The selection in alphabetical order is shown in the following Table 1.

Tab. 1: Overview of selected countries by cybersecurity level

Ranking	Country	NCSI	GCI	CEI	CSS
28	Czechia	92,12	74,37	66,60	77,73
	Ecuador	No Data Available			
29	Hungary	67,53	91,28	71,40	76,74
53	Kazachstan	48,05	93,15	42,10	61,10
64	Mexico	37,66	81,68	51,70	57,01
14	Norway	67,53	96,89	86,60	83,67
12	Poland	87,01	93,86	71,40	84,09
37	Russia	71,43	98,06	47,20	72,24
19	Slovakia	83,12	92,36	73,80	83,09
52	Ukraine	75,32	65,93	43,10	61,45
75	Uzbekistan	36,36	71,11	27,90	45,12

Source: (Seon, 2024)

Note: NCSI – National Cyber Security Index, GCI - Global Cybersecurity Index, CEI – Cybersecurity Exposure Index, CSS – Cyber Safety Score (Mean Average of NCSI, GCI, CEI).

The individual indices mentioned in Table 1 and their meaning and significance are described in the following paragraphs, including links to internet sources where the reader can find more background and information about them.

- **The National Cyber Security Index (NCSI)** is a global live index that measures countries' preparedness to prevent cyber threats and manage cyber incidents. The NCSI is also a database with publicly available evidence materials and a tool for building national cyber security capacity (National Cyber Security Index, 2024).
- **Global Cybersecurity Index (GCI)** is a trusted reference that measures countries' commitment to cybersecurity at a global level – to raise awareness of the importance and different dimensions of the issue. As cybersecurity has a broad field of application, cutting across many industries and various sectors, each country's level of development or engagement is assessed along five pillars – (i) Legal Measures, (ii) Technical Measures, (iii) Organizational Measures, (iv) Capacity Development, and (v) Cooperation – and then aggregated into an overall score (International Telecommunication Union, 2024).
- **The Cybersecurity Exposure Index (CEI)** identifies which countries are most and least exposed to cybercrime (PasswordManagers.co, 2024).
- **Cyber Safety Score (CSS)** combining data from three foremost cybersecurity authorities, namely the National Cyber Security Index, the Global Cybersecurity Index, and the Cybersecurity Exposure Index, authors have created a global ranking to present the ten countries that are, respectively, the least and most risky for internet users (Seon, 2024).

These variables indicate cybersecurity at the state level, and shifts in cybersecurity can be implemented through systemic measures at the level of the state or community of states, such as the European Union.

2 Cybersecurity and selected measures to improve it

The European Commission issues several directives and measures in digital technologies. As the importance of ICT for the economic and everyday life of citizens grows, so does its regulation and the setting of conditions for its use by both ICT service providers and qualified and ordinary users. As mentioned in the introduction, an important part of the use of ICT is trust in the data it contains and, therefore, trust in the services it provides. Data trustworthiness is one of the outcomes of ensuring ICT security. This is why ICT security and its regulation is one of the main lines of development of legislation issued by the European Union. For capacity reasons, we would like to briefly characterise two EU directives in this paper: NIS2 and DORA.

2.1 EU NIS2 Directive

The European Commission supports the overall effort to improve the cybersecurity situation in Europe through various directives, measures, and regulations. The best known of these is in information systems security, NIS2 (Network and Information Security). Its first release in 2016 was a step towards establishing a unified approach to addressing cybersecurity issues. Its extension in 2022, with effect from October 2024, requires member states to adapt it into their legal systems. This is the document "Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022", its validity is from 27 December 2022 with a delayed effective date of 17 October 2024. Its main objective is to increase **cyber resilience** across the European Union member states, ensure better cooperation between member states, and establish **common cybersecurity standards** for **critical sectors**. Compliance with the provisions of this Directive in the form of local laws is usually supervised by the state administrative authority of the relevant state, which in the Czech Republic is the "National Office for Cyber and Information Security". Its remit is mainly in cyber security, protection of classified information in information and communication systems, and cryptographic protection. In the Slovak Republic, similar competences are exercised by the 'Národný bezpečnostný úrad'.

2.1.1 What NIS2 brings new

In particular, NIS2 **significantly expands the categories of entities within its scope**. This will now include a wide range of entities not covered by the original NIS Directive - such as manufacturers of basic pharmaceutical products and medical devices, chemical manufacturers, food processors, or providers of cloud computing or public network, or electronic communications services. The new regulation will thus cover significantly more sectors than the previous NIS Directive. It will affect many entities that were not previously subject to legal obligations in the field of cybersecurity. It introduces **obligations and personal liability for the governing bodies of companies and organisations**, particularly the statutory bodies of companies. Governing bodies must oversee, approve, and be trained in cybersecurity measures. Failure to comply with the obligations set out may expose them to significant potential sanctions, including temporary disqualification from exercising management functions in the underlying entity.

Furthermore, it no longer distinguishes between '*essential service providers*' and '*digital service providers*' - as stated in the original NIS Directive, instead **entities** are now to be **divided into essential and important**, based on the sector (or its critical importance and the level of dependence of other sectors on that sector) and the size of the entity. Providers of essential services will operate under a "supervisory regime" and providers of important digital services will operate under a "light supervisory regime". The differences are in the obligation to

implement security measures and documentation and the different reporting obligations regarding security incidents and their resolution.

Further restrictions and specifications on the security of information systems apply to public and private entities operating or providing services in the EU, the types of which are listed in Annexes I and II of the NIS Directive² (i.e. to entities in designated high criticality and other critical sectors), and which are also considered medium-sized enterprises or exceed the medium-sized enterprise threshold. This includes **critical infrastructure** providers (selected hospitals, banks, energy suppliers, etc.) and **critical information infrastructure** providers (mobile operators, computer network service providers).

Like the previous NIS Directive, NIS Directive 2 requires obliged entities to take technical, operational, and organisational measures to manage risks to their networks and information systems and minimize the impact of potential incidents. In this context, the NIS2 Directive imposes new cyber security obligations on essential and critical actors, such as those related to risk management (including supply chain risk management), cyber incident reporting, and information sharing. Obligated entities must establish or update governance processes and policies to meet the newly required obligations. The NIS Directive² imposes similar obligations on essential and critical entities, but more stringent enforcement and oversight rules are set for basic entities. Failure to comply with the obligations set out in the NIS2 Directive may expose obliged entities to various sanctions, including heavy fines. For non-compliance with some of the rules set out in the NIS2 Directive (in particular the adoption of security risk management measures and compliance with the notification obligation), basic entities are liable to a **fine of at least €10,000,000** (or 2% of the total worldwide annual turnover of the undertaking). In comparison, important entities are liable to a **fine of at least €7,000,000** (or 1.4% of the total worldwide annual turnover of the undertaking). The Directive also requires EU Member States to improve their national cyber security strategies and respond to digital threats.

2.1.2 Who is covered by NIS2

The existing cyber security regulation in the Czech Republic was designed for a relatively narrow group of several hundred of the most significant organisations with an enormous impact on society. The NIS2 Directive brings a new perspective and, for the Czech Republic, the need to adapt to these changes. In terms of size, the primary concern is to be enterprises with more than 50 employees and an annual turnover or balance sheet exceeding EUR 10,000,000. The criteria for the size of an enterprise are derived from Recommendation 2003/361/EC. However, it should be said that the NIS2 Directive also provides for cases in which an entity not meeting the threshold for a medium-sized enterprise may be obliged to be an obligor - for example, an entity that is the exclusive provider of a service in a Member State that is essential for the maintenance of critical social or economic activities.

2.1.3 How the implementation is carried out

The status of implementation of the NIS2 Directive in the EU Member States is shown in Figure 2 below. The situation is as of October 2024.

Fig. 3: Implementation of NIS2 in European countries

Source: (Bird & Bird, 2024)

Five countries have already implemented the Directive in their legal framework, while six others have drafted it in local law (including the Czech Republic). Nine more are in the preparation phase, and the remaining countries have taken the position that they do not address the issues of transforming the NIS2 Directive into a local legal framework.

2.2 The EU DORA Directive

The Digital Operational Resilience Act is a significant legislative initiative proposed by the European Union (EU) to address the increasing challenges associated with digital operational resilience in the financial sector. (European Commission, 2020; European Parliament, 2022) DORA is a response to the evolving digital landscape and the recognition that the operational resilience of financial institutions is of key importance, not only for the institutions themselves but also for the broader stability of the financial system. In this section, we will introduce DORA and highlight its significance in digital operational resilience (Espinoza et al., 2023).

DORA is a legislative proposal designed to establish a comprehensive regulatory framework that focuses on enhancing the operational resilience of financial entities within the European Union. It was first introduced in September 2020 as part of the European Commission's Digital Finance Package. It is part of a broader effort to strengthen the EU's position in the global digital economy.

2.2.1 What DORA brings new

DORA encompasses several **key provisions and objectives**:

- **Operational Resilience Requirements:** DORA mandates that financial institutions maintain a defined level of operational resilience to withstand various disruptions, including cyberattacks, IT failures, and other operational incidents. This involves taking measures to ensure continuity of critical functions and protection of sensitive data.
- **Incident Reporting and Notification:** The DORA requires financial entities to promptly report and notify relevant authorities of any incidents that could significantly impact their operations.
- **Cybersecurity Standards:** Act sets standards for cybersecurity practices and requires financial institutions to implement robust cybersecurity measures to protect themselves and their customers from cyber threats. It also encourages information sharing and cooperation among financial entities to strengthen collective security.
- **Testing and Scenario Planning:** The legislation requires financial entities to conduct regular testing, including penetration and vulnerability assessments, to evaluate their operational resilience. Additionally, they must engage in scenario planning to prepare for various potential disruptions.

DORA holds significant importance for the following reasons.

- **Enhanced Financial Stability:** By imposing operational resilience requirements on financial institutions, DORA contributes to the overall stability of the financial sector. It helps prevent systemic risks and ensures that the sector can withstand operational disruptions, safeguarding the interests of depositors and investors.
- **Global Implications:** As the EU's regulatory framework for operational resilience, DORA has implications beyond the European borders. International financial institutions that operate within the EU must comply with its provisions, making it a global benchmark for operational resilience.
- **Regulatory Coordination:** DORA encourages collaboration and coordination among national authorities, regulators, and financial entities. This fosters a more cohesive and cooperative approach to addressing operational resilience challenges.
- **Customer Protection:** The Act prioritizes protecting customer data and financial assets. It instills consumer confidence by ensuring that their financial services providers take proactive measures to safeguard their interests.
- **Digital Innovation:** While focusing on resilience, DORA also recognizes the importance of digital innovation in the financial sector. It aims to strike a balance between fostering innovation and maintaining operational resilience, which is crucial in the evolving landscape of fintech and digital finance.

2.2.2 Who is covered by DORA

The Digital Operational Resilience Act represents a significant step by the European Union to address the critical issue of operational resilience in the **financial sector**. By imposing stringent requirements and standards on **financial institutions**, DORA aims to enhance financial stability, protect consumers, and create a regulatory framework relevant within the EU with global implications in an increasingly interconnected and digital financial world.

3 Conclusions

Implementing the letter of the NIS2 directive reinforces a common understanding of the security of information systems and information and communication technologies in the Member States of the European Union. It is part of a system of directives, regulations and measures that gradually unify ICT security management approaches, solutions and tools. Adopting the Directive into the legal system of individual countries is not easy. The Directive entered into force on 16 January 2023 and individual Member States have 21 months from that date to implement it in their legal systems. The requirements of the Directive should be fulfilled by 17 October 2024 and, from 18 October 2024, they must be operational. For the Czech Republic, it is estimated that the implementation will not be completed before June 2025.

Meeting DORA's requirements involves strategic planning, risk management, strong cybersecurity measures, and a culture of operational resilience. As regulatory requirements and cyber threats continue to evolve, organizations must approach compliance with a proactive and adaptable mindset. Compliance with DORA not only safeguards an organization's operations but also enhances customer trust and contributes to the overall stability of the financial system. All requirements must be met no later than January 17, 2025, when DORA becomes valid and binding.

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5 Resources

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